

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF FETUSES OF WHITE RATS UNDER CONDITIONS OF CELLULAR IMMUNODEFICIENCY OF THE MOTHER

Lis R.,

*Candidate of biological sciences,
associate professor of the department of histology, cytology and embryology
Educational institution "Grodno State Medical University"*

Aladyeva T.

*Assistant of the department of histology, cytology and embryology
Educational institution "Grodno State Medical University"*

Abstract

Objective. To reveal the teratogenic and embryotoxic effect of the mother's T-cell immune deficiency during pregnancy.

Material and Methods. The study was conducted on 43 pregnant female white rats and the fetuses obtained from them. Modeling of maternal T-cell immunodeficiency was carried out by combined administration of concanavalin A and cyclophosphamide to pregnant female white rats in the first or second half of pregnancy. Concanavalin A and cyclophosphamide were administered separately as controls. On the 20th day of pregnancy, the indices of pre- and post-implantation death of embryos, fetal and placental weights were determined, the cranio-caudal dimensions and ossification of the fetuses of rats treated by the Dawson-Dyban method and stained with alizarin red were measured.

Results. Maternal T-cell immunodeficiency in the first half of pregnancy significantly increases postimplantation death of embryos and reduces the length of the ossification anlagen of the mandibular, humerus, ulnar, ilium, ischium in rat fetuses. Concanavalin A and cyclophosphamide, administered separately, do not have such an effect. When modeling the mother's T-cell immunodeficiency in the second half of pregnancy, there are no significant changes in the studied parameters.

Conclusion. Maternal T-cell immunodeficiency prior to implantation is teratogenic for the fetus.

Keywords: cell immunodeficiency, concanavalin A, cyclophosphamide, rats, antenatal development.

Introduction

According to modern concepts, the genetic homeostasis of an organism is provided by its immune system. The immune system distinguishes the body's own structures from genetically alien ones with subsequent processing and removal of the latter [1].

It is known that the developing embryo and fetus has a different genome from the maternal one, therefore, it is an allograft for the mother. Usually, genetically alien material is rejected due to immunological reactions within two weeks, so a normal pregnancy looks paradoxical. Based on this, the mother's immune system should play one of the leading roles, both in the normal course of pregnancy and in its violation. According to literature data, modification of the immune system during pregnancy by bacterial and viral antigens, as well as medicinal immunotropic drugs, vaccines creates a risk for fetal development [2, 3, 4, 5]. In addition, a growing number of experimental studies suggest that immune dysregulation may be responsible for several, if not many, cases of habitual miscarriage of pregnancy of unknown etiology [6].

The mechanisms that ensure fetal survival are not fully known. The question of the nature of the immunological relationship between the maternal organism and the organism of the embryo and fetus is also not fully disclosed. At the same time, the mother's immune system is in a different functional state before and after implantation of the embryo. Therefore, changes in the mother's immune system during the preimplantation

period and after implantation of the embryo can lead to different effects relative to the embryo and fetus.

To answer these questions, we modified the mother's T-cell immunodeficiency during pregnancy using the combined action of concanavalin A and cyclophosphamide based on the developed biological model. Concanavalin A causes nonspecific proliferation of T-lymphocytes, and cyclophosphamide, as a cytostatic agent, stops proliferative processes, causing inhibition of T-cell immunity. [7, 8, 9].

The aim of the study was to identify the teratogenic and embryotoxic effect of maternal T-cell immunodeficiency during pregnancy.

Material and methods.

For the study, 43 pregnant female white rats, weighing 200-250 g, and fetuses from them were used. Animals of experimental, control and intact groups were kept in standard vivarium conditions.

Modification of T-cell immunodeficiency was carried out by combined administration of concanavalin A (Con A) and cyclophosphamide (CPh) to pregnant female white rats: Con A was administered at a dose of 100 mcg / kg and two days later CPh at a dose of 10 mg / kg.

In the first half of pregnancy, the joint administration of drugs to animals of the experimental group was carried out as follows: Con A was administered on the 3rd day of pregnancy (DP), and CPh - on the 5th DP (the first day of pregnancy was the day of detection of spermatozoa in a vaginal smear). The above drugs were administered separately to animals of the control

groups: Con A was introduced at the 3rd DP, and CPh - at the 5th DP.

In the second half of pregnancy, the joint administration of drugs to the animals of the experimental group was carried out as follows: Con A was administered on the 13th DP, and CPh - on the 15th DP. The animals of one of the control groups were injected with Con A at the 13th DP, the other with CPh at the 15th DP.

The animals of the intact group were not exposed to any influences.

To determine the teratogenic and embryotoxic effect of T-cell immunodeficiency of mothers pregnant females of experimental, control and intact groups were decapitated on the 20th day of pregnancy under ether anesthesia.

The determination of the embryotoxic effect of the drugs was carried out according to the indicators of pre- and post-implantation death [10]. To do this, after opening the uterus, the number of implantation sites and live fetuses were counted. The number of yellow bodies was determined in the ovaries.

Identification of possible congenital malformations and signs of circulatory disorders in the form of hemorrhages was carried out by external examination of fetuses under a magnifying glass MBS-1.

Part of the fetuses (one or two fetuses each) from the litter were fixed in 96% ethyl alcohol and treated according to the Dawson-Dyban method with the staining of ossification bookmarks with alizarin red [10]. After staining, the cranio-caudal dimensions were measured. The stained skeletons of the fetuses were defragmented and, under the magnifying glass of MBS-1, the ossification bookmarks of the following bones were measured: parietal, mandibular, scapular, clavicular, humerus, ulnar, radial, iliac, sciatic, pubic, femoral, tibial and fibula.

The experiment was conducted in compliance with the rules of humane treatment of laboratory animals in accordance with the principles of bioethics and the requirements of Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council No. 2010/63/EU of 22.09.2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes.

The obtained numerical data from each animal were analyzed by using nonparametric statistics due to small sample volumes. In descriptive statistics, median values (Me) and percentile boundaries (from 25 to 75) were determined for each indicator. Quantitative results are presented in the form of Me – median, LQ – upper bound of the lower quartile; UQ – lower bound of the upper quartile. The differences between the control and experimental groups were considered significant at $p < 0.05$ (Mann-Whitney U-test). Numerical indicators are presented in the form of tables (Tables 1-4).

Results and discussion.

When modeling T-cell immunodeficiency in the first half of pregnancy in animals of the experimental and control groups, external examination of the fetuses did not reveal congenital malformations and signs of circulatory disorders in the form of hemorrhages. The preimplantation death of embryos in animals of the experimental and control groups does not significantly

differ from intact indicators (Table 1). On the contrary, the postimplantation death of embryos significantly differs in animals of the experimental group compared with intact indicators. In animals of control groups, this indicator does not differ from intact ones (Table 1).

When modeling T-cell immunodeficiency in the second half of pregnancy in animals of the experimental and control groups, external examination of fetuses also revealed no congenital malformations and signs of circulatory disorders in the form of hemorrhages. Statistical processing of numerical indicators revealed that the indicators of preimplantation and postimplantation death of animals of all experimental groups did not differ from intact indicators (Table 2).

A fetus developing in the mother's body always has a genome different from the maternal one. The expression of fetal genes should lead to the development of immune cellular and humoral reactions of the mother against the fetus, as a xenograft. However, this paradoxically does not happen. There is a complex of mechanisms that ensure the survival of the fetus in the mother's body. And, apparently, it is the immunological mechanisms that are decisive. On the one hand, the embryo presents its antigens, on the other - the maternal immune system recognizes them and reacts.

It is known that during pregnancy, the ratio of Th1 and Th2 changes towards an increase in the latter, which may determine the suppression of the immune response to fetal antigens [11]. T-cell immunodeficiency in the first half of pregnancy can lead to a decrease in the amount of Th2, which means that this ratio may change towards a relative increase in Th1, which leads to the cancellation of the tolerance of the mother's immune system to the embryo and termination of pregnancy.

In addition, delta / gamma T-lymphocytes may be involved in the development of tolerance to the fetus. Trophoblast does not cause transplant immunity and resists NK- and CTL-mediated lysis *in vitro*. This is determined by the lack of expression of genes of the main histocompatibility complex A and B of class I. However, non-polymorphic molecules of the main histocompatibility complex G of class Ib are expressed in extravillous cytotrophoblast cells, in fetal vascular endothelial cells in chorionic villi, in amnion cells and amniotic fluid. It is gamma/delta-T lymphocytes that recognize conservative mammalian molecules on the trophoblast without the polymorphic main histocompatibility complex of class I. This leads to the triggering of the mechanisms of tolerance of the mother's immune system to fetal antigens [11]. T-cell immunodeficiency can lead to a decrease in the number of activated gamma/delta-T lymphocytes, followed by a violation of the tolerance of the mother's immune system to fetal antigens and termination of pregnancy.

However, it should be borne in mind that the process of developing tolerance of the mother's immune system in relation to fetal antigens occurs in the early stages of pregnancy after implantation. If these processes are affected during this time period, the tolerance of the mother's immune system to fetal antigens will be disrupted, which will affect the development of the fetus in the future. We can observe such an effect when

modeling T-cell immunodeficiency in the first half of pregnancy before implantation. After starting the mechanism of tolerance of the mother's immune system in relation to fetal antigens, the abolition of tolerance is a difficult reversible process. Therefore, modeling of T-cell immunodeficiency in the second half of pregnancy does not lead to an unambiguous effect of termination of pregnancy, as in its modeling in the first half of pregnancy.

With the introduction of drugs in the first half of pregnancy, there is a slight decrease in cranio-caudal size in the group of animals with simulated T-cell immunodeficiency by 5.2%. However, there are no statistically significant differences with intact indicators (Table 1). In control animals, there are also no differences with intact indicators.

The body weight of fetuses in animals of the experimental, control and intact groups is almost the same, there are no significant differences between these indicators (Table 1).

The mass of placentas in the fetuses of the experimental and control animals is slightly higher than in intact animals, but the differences with intact indicators are also statistically unreliable (Table 1).

When modeling T-cell immunodeficiency in the second half of pregnancy, cranio-caudal sizes are reduced in the fetuses of the experimental and all control groups. At the same time, in the experimental group, the differences with intact animals are statistically significant (Table 2).

Fetal body weight was statistically significantly reduced in animals of the experimental group and the control group to CPh compared with intact indicators (Table 2).

Placental mass increased statistically significantly with the introduction of Con A; with the introduction of CPh, it was statistically significantly reduced, and when modeling T-cell immunodeficiency, it does not differ from intact indicators (Table 2). However, if we proceed from the fetal-placental ratio, changes in placental masses correspond to changes in fetal body weight.

Table 1.

Indicators of preimplantation and postimplantation death of embryos, cranio-caudal dimensions of fetuses, fetal and placental masses on the 20th day of pregnancy of experimental and control animals with the introduction of ConA and CP in the first half of pregnancy (Me (Q₁÷ Q₂))

Indicator	Intact (n = 4)	Con A 3rd PD (n = 8)	CPh 5th PD (n = 3)	Con A 3rd PD + CPh 5th PD (n = 7)
Preimplantation death	0,05 (0÷0,10)	0,11 (0÷0,56)	0 (0÷0)	0,09 (0÷0,22)
Post-implantation death	0 (0÷0)	0 (0÷0,045)	0 (0÷0,09)	0,11 (0÷0,29)*
Cranio-caudal size, mm	29,0 (29÷30)	29,0 (28÷30)	29,5 (29÷30)	27,5 (26,5÷29)
Fetus weight, gr	1,93 (1,8÷2,3)	1,96 (1,86÷1,97)	1,96 (1,86÷1,97)	1,96 (1,78÷1,99)
Placenta weight, gr	0,55 (0,54÷0,56)	0,61 (0,53÷0,7)	0,60 (0,5÷0,6)	0,58 (0,5÷0,62)

Note: * – statistically significant differences with the control indicators at p<0.05

Table 2.

Indicators of preimplantation and postimplantation death of embryos, cranio-caudal dimensions of fetuses, fetal and placental masses on the 20th day of pregnancy of experimental and control animals with the introduction of ConA and CP in the second half of pregnancy (Me (Q₁÷ Q₂))

Indicator	Intact (n = 4)	Con A 13th PD (n = 7)	CPh 15th PD (n = 5)	Con A 13th PD + CPh 15th PD (n = 8)
Preimplantation death	0,05(0÷0,10)	0(0÷0)	0(0÷0)	0(0÷0)
Post-implantation death	0 (0÷0)	0,12(0÷0,13)	0,1(0÷0,11)	0,1(0÷0,18)
Cranio-caudal size, mm	29 (29÷30)	27 (27÷29)	28 (26÷29)	27(25÷27)*
Fetus weight, gr	1,93 (1,8÷2,3)	2,1 (1,9÷2,2)	1,7*(1,6÷1,84)	1,67*(1,62÷1,85)
Placenta weight, gr	0,55 (0,54÷0,56)	0,61 (0,59÷0,65)*	0,47 (0,45÷0,51)*	0,56(0,5÷0,59)

Note: * – statistically significant differences with the control indicators at p<0.05

When studying the length of ossification anlagen in fetuses during exposure in the first half of pregnancy, it was found that in the fetuses of animals of the experimental group, the length of the anlage decreases in almost all bones compared to animals of the control and intact groups. At the same time, the lengths of ossification anlagen of the mandibular, humerus, ulna, ilium, and ischium bones were significantly reduced in the fetuses of the experimental group compared to the intact ones (Table 3). The delay in ossification of the skeleton indicates a general delay in the development of offspring, which may be due to the underdevelopment of

the villous chorion. If we proceed from the premise that under the influence of the combined action of Con A and CPh, there is a violation of the tolerance of the mother's immune system in relation to the embryo, then the delay in the development of offspring is a logical response to this effect. In this case, it can be assumed that there is a violation of adequate decidualization of the endometrium due to the altered reactivity of immune cells [6], which in turn can lead to a violation of the remodeling of the spiral arteries of the uterus due to endovascular cytotrophoblast and underdevelopment

of the villous chorion in the form of impaired angiogenesis of fetal vessels in it due to the influx of highly oxygenated blood into the lacunae previously due date

[12]. Underdevelopment of the chorion will lead to fetal hypotrophy.

Table 3.

Dimensions of ossification tabs in mm: parietal, mandibular, scapular, clavicular, brachial, ulnar, radial, iliac, sciatic, pubic, femoral, tibia and fibula in fetuses on the 20th day of pregnancy of experimental and intact animals with the introduction of ConA and CP in the first half of pregnancy (Me ($Q_1 \div Q_2$))

Indicator	Intact (n = 6)	Con A 3rd PD (n = 10)	CPh 5th PD (n = 6)	Con A 3rd PD + CPh 5th PD (n = 10)
Parietal	4,65(4,5÷4,7)	4,65(4,5÷4,8)	4,6(4,5÷4,6)	4,3(4÷4,7)
Mandibular	6,4(6,4÷6,7)	6,5(6,3÷6,7)	6,4(6,4÷6,5)	6,2(5,7÷6,4) *
Scapular	2,15(2,1÷2,2)	2,2(2,1÷2,3)	2,25(2,1÷2,3)	2,0(1,8÷2,2)
Clavicular	2,55(2,2÷2,7)	2,65(2,5÷2,8)	2,5(2,4÷2,5)	2,45(2,2÷2,55)
Brachial	2,45(2,3÷2,5)	2,35(2,2÷2,5)	2,4(2,3÷2,4)	2,15(1,9÷2,3) *
Ulnar	2,35(2,3÷2,5)	2,3(2,2÷2,4)	2,3(2,3÷2,4)	2,2(2,0÷2,3) *
Radial	1,8(1,7÷1,9)	1,8(1,7÷1,8)	1,8(1,8÷1,8)	1,75(1,55÷1,85)
Iliac	1,55(1,5÷1,6)	1,4(1,4÷1,5)	1,4(1,4÷1,5)	1,3(1,2÷1,45) *
Sciatic	0,5(0,4÷0,6)	0,5(0,4÷0,55)	0,5(0,5÷0,6)	0,3(0,1÷0,5) *
Pubic	0(0÷0,1)	0,05(0÷0,2)	0(0÷0,2)	0(0÷0,175)
Femoral	1,55(1,5÷1,8)	1,5(1,4÷1,6)	1,55(1,5÷1,6)	1,5(1,25÷1,6)
Tibia	1,9(1,7÷2,0)	1,85(1,7÷2,0)	1,9(1,9÷1,9)	1,75(1,55÷1,95)
Fibula	1,65(1,5÷1,8)	1,7(1,6÷1,8)	1,65(1,6÷1,7)	1,5(1,3÷1,65)

Note: * – statistically significant differences with the control indicators at $p < 0.05$

Table 4.

Dimensions of ossification tabs in mm: parietal, mandibular, scapular, clavicular, brachial, ulnar, radial, iliac, sciatic, pubic, femoral, tibia and fibula in fetuses on the 20th day of pregnancy of experimental and intact animals with the introduction of ConA and CP in the first half of pregnancy (Me ($Q_1 \div Q_2$))

Indicator	Intact (n = 6)	Con A 13th PD (n = 11)	CPh 15th PD (n = 9)	Con A 13th PD + CPh 15th PD (n = 11)
Parietal	4,65(4,5÷4,7)	4,5(4,1÷4,8)	4,2(3,7÷4,4)	4,4(4÷4,5)
Mandibular	6,4(6,4÷6,7)	6,4(6,3÷6,7)	6,3(6,2÷6,4)	6,3(5,9÷6,4)
Scapular	2,15(2,1÷2,2)	2,1(2,0÷2,2)	2,1(2,1÷2,1)	2,1(1,9÷2,2)
Clavicular	2,55(2,2÷2,7)	2,5(2,4÷2,6)	2,5(2,4÷2,5)	2,5(2,4÷2,6)
Brachial	2,45(2,3÷2,5)	2,3(2,1÷2,5)	2,3(2,1÷2,3)	2,2(2÷2,4)
Ulnar	2,35(2,3÷2,5)	2,3(2,1÷2,4)	2,2(2,2÷2,3)	2,2(2,0÷2,4)
Radial	1,8(1,7÷1,9)	1,8(1,7÷1,9)	1,8(1,6÷1,8)	1,7(1,5÷1,8)
Iliac	1,55(1,5÷1,6)	1,4(1,3÷1,5)	1,4(1,4÷1,5)	1,3(1,2÷1,4) *
Sciatic	0,5(0,4÷0,6)	0,5(0,4÷0,6)	0,4(0,3÷0,4) *	0,45(0,4÷0,55)
Pubic	0(0÷0,1)	0(0÷0,2)	0(0÷0)	0(0÷0)
Femoral	1,55(1,5÷1,8)	1,5(1,4÷1,6)	1,5(1,4÷1,5)	1,5(1,3÷1,7)
Tibia	1,9(1,7÷2,0)	1,8(1,7÷2,0)	1,7(1,7÷1,8)	1,8(1,7÷2,0)
Fibula	1,65(1,5÷1,8)	1,6(1,4÷1,7)	1,6(1,5÷1,6)	1,6(1,5÷1,7)

Note: * – statistically significant differences with the control indicators at $p < 0.05$

When modeling T-cell immunodeficiency in the second half of pregnancy, the above dependence is not observed. The length of ossification anlagen of almost all bones in animals of the experimental and control groups does not differ significantly from intact indicators. Only in two cases is a significant decrease in the length of the ossification anlage observed: the iliac bone in the fetuses of the experimental group and the pubic bone in the control group with the introduction of CPh on the 15th DP (Table 4).

Conclusions

Modeling of T-cell immunodeficiency in the first half of pregnancy in rats before implantation leads to a

violation of the formation of the bone skeleton in rat fetuses and an increase in post-implantation death of offspring. Violation of the formation of internal organs is a sign of the teratogenicity of this effect. At the same time, the separate administration of ConA and CPh preparations in the doses used does not lead to a teratogenic effect.

Modeling of maternal T-cell immunodeficiency after implantation does not lead to the above effects, which can be explained by the resistance to external influences of the mother's immune system's tolerance to fetal antigens.

References

1. Йегер, Л. Клиническая иммунология и аллергология / Л. Йегер – М.: Медицина, 1990. – Т.3. – 586 с.
2. Лис, Р.Е., Влияние бактериального липополисахарида продигиозана на антенатальный нейрогенез коры больших полушарий плодов белых крыс / Р.Е. Лис, Ю.И. Бандажевский // Известия АН БССР. Серия биологических наук. – 1986. – №4. – С. 76-79.
3. Robbins, J. Pathogens and the placental fortress / J. Robbins, A. Bakardjiev // *Current Opinion in Microbiology*. – 2012. – V.15, N1. – P. 36-43.
4. Soumiya, H. Prenatal immune challenge compromises the normal course of neurogenesis during development of the mouse cerebral cortex / H. Soumiya, H. Fukumitsu, S. Furukawa // *Journal of Neuroscience Research*. – 2011. – V.89, N10. – P. 1575-1585.
5. Tang, A. Recent thoughts on management and prevention of recurrent early pregnancy loss / A. Tang, S. Quenby // *Current Opinion in Obstetrics and Gynecology*. – 2010. – V.22, N6. – P. 446-451.
6. Ticconi, C. Endometrial immune dysfunction in recurrent pregnancy loss / C. Ticconi, A. Pietropolli, N. Di Simone, E. Piccione, A. Fazleabas // *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. – 2019 – V. 20, N21.– P. 5332; doi: 10.3390/ijms20215332.
7. Кондратьева, Т.К. Природа иммунодефицита, индуцированного инъекциями лектинов и циклофосфамида / Т.К. Кондратьева, Н.В. Михеева, Л.Н. Фонталин // *Бюллетень экспериментальной биологии и медицины*. – 1988.– № 8. – С. 195-198.
8. Леонтьева, Т.И. Исследование иммуотропной активности циклофосфана / Т.И. Леонтьева, Н.Е. Гладкова, Б.С. Утешев // *Фармакология и токсикология* – 1988. – Т.51, №6. – С. 60-65.
9. Фонталин, Л.Н. Т-клеточный иммунодефицит у мышей, получивших лектин и циклофосфамид / Л.Н. Фонталин, Т.К. Кондратьева, Н.В. Михеева // *Бюллетень экспериментальной биологии и медицины*. – 1988.– №7. – С. 75-78.
10. Дыбан, А.П. Основные методические подходы к тестированию активности химических веществ / А.П. Дыбан, В.С. Баранов, И.М. Акимова // *Архив анатомии, гистологии и эмбриологии*. – 1970. – № 10. – С. 89-100.
11. Szekeres-Barto, J. Immunological relationship between the mother and the fetus. / J. Szekeres-Barto // *Reviews of Immunology*. – 2002. – V. 21. – N 6. – P. 471-495.
12. Huppertz, B. Trophoblast invasion: remodeling of spiral arteries and beyond. in: saito s. (eds) preeclampsia. / *Comprehensive gynecology and obstetrics*. Springer, Singapore. – 2018. – V. 4. – P. 47-62.